

Table 2. Distinguishing morphological characters of Pant Dhan 10.

Character	Description
Height	92 cm
Seedling vigor	Good
Lodging	Resistant
Plant type	Semidwarf, ideal
Leaf sheath	Green
Tillering	High (15-20 tillers/plant)
Flag leaf	Erect, narrow, short
Photoperiod sensitivity	Insensitive
Panicle length	22.5 cm
Apiculus color	Green
Awning	Awnless
1,000-grain wt	26 g
Grain type	Long, slender
Kernel length	6.9 mm
Kernel breadth	2.2 mm
L-B ratio	3.1
Head rice recovery	63%
Abdominal white	Absent

maggot, whitebacked planthopper, cutworm, and gundhi bug in the national screening nursery. (See Table 2 for morphological characteristics of Pant Dhan 10.) ■

A high-yielding mutant line of traditional aromatic rice cultivar Gobindabhog

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Gobindabhog is a popular traditional aromatic cultivar of West Bengal, India. It has small fine grain and low yield potential. Modern nonscented cultivars are not a replacement for it. Demand is high for Gobindabhog in the domestic market, and farmers get a premium for producing it. Increasing the yield of this variety would be rewarding for them.

In a research project sponsored by the Department of Atomic Energy, Government of India, a high-yielding mutant line (124-17-4) was created through irradiation by using a 25-kr dose of gamma rays.

Mutant line IET13541(124-17-4) was tested in the Initial Basmati Varietal Trial and the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program across 11 locations during 1992 wet season. The line

yielded an average of 4.6 t/ha, slightly more than the 4.5 t/ha of check Pusa Basmati. It ranked fifth out of 17 entries for yield performance. The line yielded an average of 4.3 t/ha compared with 3.2 t/ha for Gobindabhog in 4 yr of replicated yield trials at the IA Farm. Three farmers who grew IET13541(124-17-4) reported yields of more than 4 t/ha.

The line is about 135 cm tall, 20 cm shorter than its parent. It has erect, broad, dark green leaves and compact tillers and panicles. It is photoperiod-sensitive, matures in 155 d, and tolerates 70 kg N/ha.

In national screening nurseries, it showed resistance to gall midge, stem

borer, brown planthopper, blast, and sheath rot. It also resisted bacterial blight at the IA Farm.

The short, bold, white kernels are 3.7 mm long and 1.9 mm wide, with a L-B ratio of 2.0. The 1,000-grain weight is 10.7 g, and the original aroma remains. Alkali spreading value is 2.3 and amylose content, 23.4%. The grain elongates up to 6.3 mm after cooking. Yields of hulled, milled, and head rice are 78.5, 73.5, and 54.5%, respectively. The high yield potential of IET13541(124-17-4) is because it has more grains/panicle than its parent. ■

Pant Dhan 11, a new rice variety for the lower hills of Uttar Pradesh, India

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Pant Dhan 11 (UPR 653-6-1-1-2) was developed by pedigree method after hybridization from the F₂ seed of IR17251 (VL 206/Dagi). It is a semi-dwarf that matures in 118-125 d, depending upon elevation. It is suitable for transplanting in hills up to 900 m in elevation in UP.

Pant Dhan 11 yielded consistently better than national check Himdhan and local checks in the All India Coordinated Varietal Trials (Table 1). In farmers' field demonstrations in Kumaon and Garhwal divisions of UP, Pant Dhan 11 yielded a mean of 4.7 t/ha compared with 4.4 t/ha for Pant Dhan 6 and 3.5 t/ha for local varieties.

Pant Dhan 11 is resistant to leaf blast and moderately resistant to bacterial blight under epiphytotic conditions. It has shown a moderately resistant reaction to brown planthopper in glasshouse screening. (See Table 2 for morphological characteristics of Pant Dhan 11.) ■

Table 2. Distinguishing morphological characters of Pant Dhan 11.

Character	Description
Height	90 cm
Seedling vigor	Good
Lodging	Resistant
Plant type	Semidwarf, compact
Leaf sheath color	Green
Tillering	Medium (10-12 tillers/plant)
Flag leaf	Erect
Photoperiod sensitivity	Insensitive
Apiculus color	Green
Awning	Awnless to tip-awned
Grains/panicle	90-100
Kernel length	6.5 mm
Kernel breadth	2.7 mm
L-B ratio	2.95
Grain type	Long, bold
Head rice recovery	52%
Abdominal white	Absent

Table 1. Mean performance of Pant Dhan 11 in national trials in the hills of UP, India. 1985-87.

Trial ^a	Year	Mean yield (t/ha)			% increase over	
		Pant Dhan 11	Himdhan (check)	Local variety (check)	Himdhan	Local variety
PVT-2 (H)	1985	4.2	3.9	3.9	7.6	7.6
PVT-2 (H)	1986	2.3	1.3	1.1	76.9	109.1
UVT-2 (H)	1987	3.9	2.8	3.5	39.2	11.4
Mean		3.5	2.7	2.8	25.9	21.4

^aPVT-2 (H) = preliminary variety trial-2 (hills). UVT-2 (H) = uniform variety trial-2 (hills).